

Green chemical pathways : a need of the day^ψ

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Introduction

In the glorious days of 1950's and 1960's chemists envisioned chemistry as the solution to a host of society's needs. Indeed, they created many things which improve the quality of life on earth like dyes, plastics, cosmetics and other materials. At the same time chemistry brought about medical revolution i.e. through antibiotics which conquered infectious disease. All these things prove DuPont slogan, "Better things for better living through chemistry".

But there are some adverse outcome due to discovery of drugs, insecticides, herbicides, fertilizers, etc. which causes a cancerous grip of the air, water, soil and noise pollution on earth that grabbed this world like an octopus, e.g. DDT which accumulated in birds and causes egg shell thinning and nesting failures results in decline of that species. Refrigerent like CFCs depletes the ozone layer remarkably which protects our earth from harmful UV rays of sun. So there are several advantages and disadvantages of chemistry, but there is main disadvantage i.e. pollution and this marked the beginning of green chemistry by the middle of 20th century.

The term "Green Chemistry" was coined by Professor Paul Anastas, who is known as the father of Green Chemistry, at US Environmental Protection Agency. Green Chemistry is the effort of reducing or eliminating the use or generation of hazardous substances in the design, manufacture and application of chemical products¹.

Green Chemistry is defined as environmentally benign chemical synthesis. It is science based, non regulatory and economically driven approach to achieving the goals of environmental protection²⁻⁷. The ultimate value of green chemistry lies in its applicability for the new millennium. So the challenge to reduce the waste, the toxicity of chemical and the amount of energy used, while still providing the goods that society needs, is overcome through green chemistry.

Green chemistry has been referred by a number of alternate name like 'Clean Chemistry', 'Atom Economy', 'Benign by Design Chemistry'⁶, 'Sustainable Chemistry'⁸, 'Ecofriendly Chemistry' and 'Environmentally Benign Chemistry'. While Green Chemistry encompasses human health and the environment, it is guided by very specific principles of chemical practice. These principles are summarised as the twelve principles of Green Chemistry¹.

The twelve principles of Green Chemistry

The principles of Green Chemistry can be applied to almost every part of chemistry, that includes synthesis of molecules with a desired structure and property, catalysis of a process, less polluting reaction conditions, etc.

(1) Prevention : It is better to prevent waste than to treat or clean up waste after it has been created.

(2) Atom economy : Synthetic methods should be designed to maximize the incorporation of all materials used in the process into the final product.

(3) Less hazardous chemical synthesis : Wherever practicable, synthetic methods should be designed to use and generate substances that possess little or no toxicity to human health and the environment.

(4) Designing safer chemicals : Chemical products should be designed to affect their desired function while minimizing their toxicity.

(5) Safer solvents and auxiliaries : The use of auxiliary substance (solvents, separation agents, etc.) should be minimized whenever possible and should be made innocuous when used.

(6) Design for energy efficiency : Energy requirements of chemical processes should be recognised for their environmental and economic impacts and should be minimized. If possible, synthetic methods should be conducted at ambient temperature and pressure.

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

(7) Use renewable feedstocks : Raw material or feedstock should be renewable rather than depleting whenever technically and economically practicable.

(8) Reduce derivatives : Unnecessary derivatization (use of blocking groups, protection/deprotection and temporary modification of physical/chemical processes) should be minimized or avoided if possible, because such steps require additional reagents and can generate waste.

(9) Catalysis : Catalytic reagents (as selective as possible) are superior to stoichiometric reagents. Using catalytic reagents creates opportunities for increased selectivity, better yield, and feasibility of non feasible reaction.

(10) Design for degradation : Chemical products should be designed so that at the end of their function they break down into innocuous degradation products and do not persist in the environment.

(11) Real-time analysis for pollution prevention : Analytical methodologies need to be further developed to allow for real-time, in-process monitoring and control prior to the formation of hazardous substances.

(12) Inherently safer chemistry for accident prevention : Substances and the form of a substance used in chemical process should be chosen to minimize the potential for chemical accidents including releases, explosions and fires.

Green Chemistry has changed our life style in many ways. Like now a days dry cleaning of clothes is done with the use of liquid CO₂ and a surfactant, thereby eliminating a need of halogenated solvents like PERC (perchloroethylene Cl₂C=CCl₂)⁹. This technology is known as Micell Technology and was developed by Joseph De Simons, Timothy Romack and James McClain. In the same way, hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is used with some activators like TAML¹⁰ activators as a bleaching agent rather than the use of halogenated compounds.

Green chemicals

The increasing local and global concern for environmental pollution offers incentive to explore new green materials for safeguarding the environment. Green materials have been applied in the design of benign synthetic processes to eliminate or minimize pollution at the source, as well as in the remediation of a variety of existing environmental pollution problems. The overall development of green materials or chemicals can be characterized in three parts :

(1) Green reagent, (2) Green catalyst and (3) Green solvent.

(1) *Green reagent* :

The criteria of efficiency, availability and effect of the

green reagent on environment is used to carry out the transformation of selected feedstock into the target molecules. Various types of green reagents are used but commonly used are DMC and polymer supported reagent. DMC is a non toxic, environmentally safe reagent that can be used in organic synthesis as a green substitute for toxic intermediates such as phosgene in carbonylation reactions and dimethylsulphate (DMS) and methyl chloride in methylation reaction. Some applications of DMC in organic synthesis^{11,12} are :

(iii) Tundo *et al.*^{13,14} developed a method to methylate active methylene compounds selectively using DMC in which no inorganic salts are produced.

In the above reaction DMC acts as an organic oxidant¹⁵.

Polymer supported reagents are those in which ordinary reagents are bound to polymer support. Examples are polymer supported peracid¹⁶ (used for epoxidation of alkene), polymer supported chromic acid^{17,18}, polymeric thioanisoyl resin¹⁹, sulfonazide polymer²⁰, polymeric phenyl thiomethyl lithium reagent²¹, poly-N-bromosuccinimide²², etc. Polymer supported reagents are used in clean and efficient synthesis of azo dyes²³.

(2) Green catalyst :

Catalyst plays a major role in establishing the economic strength of chemical industry and developing clean chemical processes and products. Some different type of catalysts used are :

(i) **Acid catalyst :** Now a days the traditional catalyst like HF, monomerclensis acid etc. are replaced by green catalyst like fluorided silica-alumina catalyst, microencapsulated Lewis acid, heteropoly acid catalyst, zeolites etc. Heteropoly acids are used for hydration of isobutylene and polymerization of tetrahydrofuran²⁴⁻²⁶. Microencapsulated Lewis acids were used in the reactions like Michael²⁷, Friedel-Craft²⁸, Mannich²⁹, iminoaldol reaction³⁰.

[MCSc(OTf)₃] = Microencapsulated scandium trifluoromethane sulfonate

(ii) **Oxidation catalyst :** Used in the liquid phase partial oxidation of organic substrates^{31,32}.

(iii) **Basic catalyst :** These catalyst are useful in the alkylation of phenol, side chain alkylation and isomerisation reaction^{33,34}.

(iv) **Photocatalyst :** One of the more neglected techniques available to Green Chemistry is photochemistry and photocatalysis is frontier of photochemistry. Photocatalysis is a phenomenon, where an electron-hole pair is generated on exposing semiconducting materials to light of suitable energy. Thus, the chemical reactions that occur in the presence of a semiconductor and light are termed as photo-

catalytic reactions. Photocatalysis is a main tool in dealing with the worldwide problems of environmental pollution and wastewater treatment. Photocatalysis is useful for treatment of inorganic contaminants, organic contaminants, dyes, surfactants, pesticides, industrial pollutants, bacterial pollutants from drinking water, etc. Few examples are given below :

The photocatalytic reduction of the pollutant Hg(II) salts using TiO₂ photocatalyst (Hombikat UV 100) was studied by Khalil *et al.*³⁵. Chen and Ray³⁶ removed some toxic metal ions from wastewater by photocatalysis. Photocatalytic degradation of Co(II) and Cu(II) over ZnO was reported by Dangi *et al.*^{37,38}. The mechanism is as follows :

Tanaka *et al.*³⁹ reported the photocatalytic degradation of chloral hydrate (a toxic compound, used for the synthesis of insecticides) in aqueous semiconductor suspension involving [•]OH radicals as oxidizing species.

Photodegradation of 4-chlorophenol in water (sensitized by semiconductor) was reported by Al-Sayyed *et al.*⁴⁰. The photocatalytic degradation of various dyes over ZnO semiconductor was reported⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. A common tentative mechanism for photocatalytic bleaching of dyes has been proposed.

Recently, photobleaching of Rhodamine-B over ZnO was reported by Mansoori *et al.*⁴⁵. Similarly photocatalytic degradation of some surfactants like cetylpyridinium chloride⁴⁶, sodium lauryl sulfate⁴⁷ and dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide⁴⁸ over titanium dioxide has been reported.

Semiconductor mediated photocatalyzed degradation of two selective pesticide derivatives, terbacil and 2,4,5-tribromoimidazole in aqueous suspension has been reported by Muneer *et al.*⁴⁹. The photocatalytic removal of bacterial pollutants from drinking water was carried out by Dunlop *et al.*⁵⁰ whereas Vamathevan *et al.*⁵⁷ investigated photo-

catalytic oxidation of organics in water using pure and silver modified TiO₂ particles. Looking to the present trends, the time is not far off, when this method will be received as an alternative "Green Chemical" technology by the scientific community all over the world for wastewater treatment.

(v) *Phase transfer catalyst (PTC)*: The basic functions of PTC is to remove the interface between two immiscible reactants. It involves the transfer of ion or organic molecule between two liquid phases or a liquid and solid phase. It works as a transport shuttle. PTC have several advantages relevant to green synthesis; higher productivity, higher selectivity, ease of product separation, use of less hazardous solvents, etc. PTC is used in organic synthesis^{52,54} like

Above procedure is far superior to the conventional method⁵³.

(ii) Noyori synthesis of adipic acid⁵⁴.

(iii) *N*-Alkylation of β -lactams is an important step in the synthesis of norcardione⁵⁵.

Commonly used catalyst for solid-liquid systems are crown ether and polyglycol ether. e.g. esterification⁵⁶ and elimination⁵⁷.

In the absence of crown ether syn elimination takes place with 91% yield along with 9% of anti elimination. Solid-liquid solvent free phase transfer catalysis (PTC) and acidic catalysis in dry media were applied, as green chemistry procedures, to the synthesis under mild conditions of long chain aliphatic esters of interest in the cosmetic field⁵⁸.

(vi) *Polymer supported catalyst*: The catalyst which is

linked to a polymer backbone and used in catalyzing different reactions in homogenous phase are known as polymer supported catalyst. Examples are polystyrene aluminium chlorides⁵⁹ (used for hydrolysis of acetal and for formation of ether from alcohol), polymeric super-acid catalyst⁶⁰ (used for cracking and isomerisation of alkanes), polystyrene metallaporphyrins⁶¹ (used for oxidation of thiols), polymer supported phase transfer catalyst⁶², etc.

(vii) *Biocatalyst*: Usually chemical reactions are carried out in rigorous condition, while biocatalyst offers the possibility of carrying the reaction without formation of toxic and carcinogenic ingredients. There are many valuable compounds made in lower volume⁶³ by biocatalyst. These include lactic acid, malic acid, L-aspartic acid and other amino acids⁶⁴, flavors and fragrances⁶⁵, steroids, vitamins human growth hormones and many enzymes⁶⁶. L-Malate is made by hydration of fumarate using a fumarase from *Breviibacterium flavum*. It can also be produced in upto 109 g/L by a strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*⁶⁷.

Solid enzymes have been used as fixed bed catalysts with vaporized substances⁶⁸. As an example, allyl alcohol has been oxidized to acrolein with aldehyde dehydrogenase.

Enzymes and microbes can be used in a variety of ways in organic synthesis⁶⁹. These includes oxidation⁷⁰⁻⁷², reduction⁷³, acylation, halogenation, hydrolysis, etc. Glycine has been converted into L-serine by reaction with formaldehyde using *E. coli*⁷⁴. Propionic acid can also be made from hemicelluloses in wood⁷⁵. Long chain unsaturated fatty acids that are of interest for good health, can also be produced biocatalytically. Most of the industrial applications of enzymes dealt with the production of fine chemicals or drugs⁷⁶.

(3) Green solvents :

The use of classical solvents in organic synthesis, such as acetone, THF, diethylether and others, produces a large amount of environmentally toxic waste. The difficulty in treating these materials, their separation and destruction, dramatically increases the total cost of production for a compound. Thus, the use of alternative cleaner technologies has become important for both academia and industry.

Some hazardous solvent like benzene, methylene chloride, diethyl ether can be replaced by solvent likes toluene, benzotrifluoride, methyl *t*-butyl ether respectively. Now a days CO₂ and water are emerging as potential green solvents. CO₂ is isolated from the environment and more environmentally benign and less toxic than other solvent. Supercritical CO₂ can be used in the reaction process as ecofriendly alternative and its solubility limitation can be overcome by using non toxic ammonium carboxylate perfluoropolyether as surfactant. Supercritical CO₂ has been used to replace volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in spray paints.

According to current research organic solvents can be replaced by water provides less cost, safety and simple operation. In general water promotes many reactions at temperature higher than 100°C. These includes the Diels-Alder⁷⁷, Heck⁷⁸, Michael, Knoevenagel reaction, benzoin condensation⁷⁹, Baeyer-Villiger oxidation⁸⁰, dipolar cycloaddition, Claisen rearrangement, hydroformylation, etc.

Darzens condensation of benzaldehyde with phenacyl chloride proceeds very efficiently in a water suspension medium⁸³. Cornely *et al.*⁸⁴ reported dimethyl carbonate (DMC)-water to be an environmentally benign solvent system for ruthenium tetraoxide oxidation of various substances including alkenes, alkynes, alcohols, ethers, etc.

Water should be obviously an alternative to commercial solvents in some industrial processes but a better solution is offered by **Ionic Liquids (ILs)**, which are now receiving attention as "**Green Solvents**". The first known ionic liquid ethylammonium nitrate was discovered in 1914 by Walden, but since then a large variety of ionic liquids with m.p. < 100°C have been prepared. They possess highly ionic character, virtual absence of vapor pressure, lack of flammability and above all ease of use. Ionic liquids find applications in Diels-Alder cycloadditions⁸⁵, hydrogenation⁸⁶, Friedel-Crafts reactions^{87,88}, etc. Selective catalytic oxidation of benzyl alcohol and alkylbenzenes in ionic liquids has been reported by Seddon and Stark⁸⁹. The condensation reaction of 4-oxo-(4*H*)-1-benzopyran-3-carbaldehydes and of aromatic aldehydes with 3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazolin-5-(4*H*)-one were carried out in ionic liquid-ethylammonium nitrate, at room temperature in shorter times with higher yields of 78-92% and 70-75%, respectively than conventional methods⁹⁰.

Nguyen *et al.*⁹¹ used ILs 1-octyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide/iodide as catalytic green solvents and solvents for nucleophilic conversion of fatty alcohols to alkyl halides. Esterification of carboxylic acids with alcohols was carried out in Bronsted acidic ionic liquid 1-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (a green catalyst)⁹².

Recently, Mannich reaction using acidic ionic liquids as catalysts and solvents was reported by Zheo *et al.*⁹³. A lot of research work is taking place in the field of ionic liquids as Green catalyst and solvent, thus giving chemist yet another opportunity to invent or redevelop Green Chemical Processes, a step closer to Sustainable Chemistry.

Organic synthesis in solid state

The use of solid support in reaction has been widely reported as an appropriate methodology for the reduction of waste and minimization of energy use, in line with the principle of green chemistry. In this aspect, the organic synthesis will be presented in two parts :

(i) Solid phase organic synthesis without using any solvent.

(ii) Solid supported organic synthesis.

One of the most striking characteristics of solid state reaction is the high degree of conversion to a product that is achieved in many cases. A number of 2'-hydroxy-4',6'-dimethylchalcones undergo a solid state intramolecular Michael type addition to yield the corresponding flavones.

Similarly Dieckman condensation of diethyl adipate and pimelate proceed very well in presence of diesters and powdered Bu^tOK

The dimerisation reaction of [60] Fullerene in presence of KCN proceeded in solid state to give [2+3] adduct⁹⁶.

The reaction of aldehyde with (-) ephedrine or (+) pseudoephedrine by keeping powdered reaction mixture at room temperature give quantitatively the corresponding oxazolidines⁹⁷. Solid state reaction of anilines and aromatic aldehyde give various azomethines⁹⁸.

In solid supported organic synthesis the reactants stirred in a suitable solvent and the solution is stirred thoroughly with a suitable adsorbent or solid support like silicagel, alumina, phyllosilicate (Mⁿ⁺-montmorillonite), etc. after stirring the solvent is removed. An efficient synthesis of benzopyrano-pyrimidines using different solid support has been observed with improved yield⁹⁹.

Emerging green technologies

In current aspects development of more sustainable products and energy efficient processes with reducing waste are discussed in emerging green technologies. By using these technologies energy input reduces, improvement of selectivity, shortening of reaction time occurs. Some reactions which are not possible with single heating, can be possible with above technique. Use of energy sources like light, microwave, ultrasound and electricity are more clean, and efficient. Particularly for bulk chemicals, development of much more energy efficient processes provides significant commercial benefits. Emerging techniques, in the overall development of "Green Chemistry", can be categorised in following parts :

(1) Photochemistry, (2) Microwave chemistry, (3) Sonochemistry and (4) Electrochemistry.

(1) Photochemistry :

Light is environmentally benign, leaving no residue to be removed in the workup of a reaction. A photochemical reaction occurs when an atom or molecule absorbs light [Grotthuss-Draper law]. Further one photon of light can activate only one molecules [Stark-Einstein law]. When a photon is absorbed by a molecule or atom it must transfer all its energy to atom or molecule and promoted to higher energy state. The energy required for promotion from ground state to lowest excited state falls in ultraviolet and visible region of electromagnetic spectrum. Light can catalyzed some reactions that are difficult or impossible in other ways (e.g. cycloaddition¹⁰⁰). Solar furnace is used for isomerisation, catalytic cyclisation and purification of water¹⁰¹. Dithianes, benzyl ethers and related compounds have been cleaved by the use of visible light with a dye¹⁰². A combi-

nation of visible light and water was used in cyclization to produce substituted pyridines with almost no byproducts¹⁰³. Oxidation of hydrocarbons in zeolites with blue light gives improved selectivity¹⁰⁴. Photooxidation of cyclohexane in the presence of titanium dioxide gave 85.4% cyclohexanone, 2.6% cyclohexanol and 12% carbon dioxide¹⁰⁵. Acylhydroquinones can be produced from 1,4-benzoquinone and an aldehyde using light from a sunlamp¹⁰⁶. In contrast to the usual acylation with an acid chloride, this process produce no byproduct salt.

Benzonitrile in methanolic potassium hydroxide can be hydrolyzed to benzamide in 96% yield using an oxophosphorpyrin catalyst with light > 420 nm at 20°C¹⁰⁷. Photo redox reactions can be carried out with semiconductors. Irradiation of nitrobenzene in the presence of zinc oxide particles in alcohol produce phenyl hydroxyl amine in 73% yield¹⁰⁸. Solar light induced photocatalytic oxidation of benzyl alcohol using heteropolyoxometalate catalysts of the type $[\text{S}_2\text{M}_{18}\text{O}_{62}]^{4-}$ was reported¹⁰⁹. The photoreactions between 1,4-quinones and aldehydes (Photo-Friedel-Craft acylation of quinones), yielding acylated hydroquinones as sole products, were investigated under artificial and solar irradiation conditions¹¹⁰. A photochemical method to remove uranium from a phosphate containing waste in high yield is reported by Evans *et al.*¹¹¹.

(2) Microwave chemistry :

Microwaves have wavelength between 1 cm and 1 m (frequencies 30 GHz to 300 Hz). These are similar to frequency of radar and telecommunication devices. In order to avoid interference with these systems, the frequency of radiation that can be emitted by household and industrial microwave oven is regulated and most of the appliances

operate at a fixed frequency of 2.45 GHz. In 1986 two pioneering publications¹¹² (one from Canada and the other from the United States) appeared, that described several synthetic organic reactions conducted in domestic microwave oven. The use of microwave energy¹¹³ instead of conventional heating, often results in good yields in very short time. Lewis¹¹⁴ stated enhancement of a chemical reaction in microwave as compared to conventional heating. Reaction can manifest in several ways including (1) highly accelerated reaction rates, (2) improved yield in many cases, (3) stereo- or regioselectivity in some cases, (4) reduction in side products, (5) limited amount of solvents (or no solvent in special cases) needed as reaction medium, (6) successful product formation in some reactions that fail under conventional conditions and (7) simplification and improvement of classical synthetic method etc.

A recent survey shows that more than a thousand publications have appeared on microwave mediated chemical reactions¹¹⁵. Microwave heats some certain substances not others due to selective absorption of microwave by polar molecules (Non polar molecules are inert). Reactions can be classified in two categories in microwave : (a) reaction with solvent and (b) solvent free reactions.

Various types of reactions are conducted in microwave. 2,3-Dimethyl indole was obtained with 67% yield from phenylhydrazine and butane-2-one at 220°C for 30 min¹¹⁶.

Hydrolysis of benzyl chloride into benzyl alcohol takes 3 min in microwave while conventional method takes 35 min¹¹⁷.

Various types of oxidation¹¹⁸⁻¹²⁰ can be carried out in MW, e.g.

In microwave some organic reactions can be carried out with the use of organic solvent like esterification of alcohol^{117,121}, esterification of benzyl ethers using LnBr_3 ¹²², Fries rearrangement¹²³, orthoester Claisen rearrangement¹²⁴, Diels-Alder reaction, decarboxylation¹²⁵, chalcones synthesis, aziridine synthesis^{126,127}, etc.

p-Cresyl acetate

2-Hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone (85%)

Hydrogenation of β -lactams using ammonium formate as hydrogen donor and Pd/C as catalyst has been described by Bose and co-workers¹²⁸. Using solid support various organic reactions¹²⁹⁻¹³¹ can be carried out in microwave. Cyclo condensation of *N*-(carbo trifluoro methyl) ortho arylene diamines¹³² on clay K10 in dry media under MW irradiation for 2 min give high yield while by classical heating only traces of heterocycles are observed.

Acetophenone oxime

Acetanilide (91%)

Condensation of β -formyl enamides with cyano methylenes under microwave irradiation is catalysed by basic alumina to afford fused pyrimidines in excellent yields in very short time¹³³. Hantzsh dihydropyridine synthesis¹³⁴ and oxidation of β,β -disubstituted enamines over $\text{KMnO}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ¹³⁵ is also reported in MW with shorter time and high yield as compared to conventional heating. Similarly imidazole synthesis¹³⁶, thiadiazepines synthesis¹³⁷, carbohydrate glycosylations¹³⁸ can be carried out in MW by using solvent.

Reaction of carboxylic acid with benzyl halides does not occur when heated conventionally but could be performed in MW by using quaternary ammonium salt as a catalyst. So, by using phase transfer catalyst some important organic reactions like ester synthesis^{139,140}, ether synthesis¹⁴¹, *N*-alkylation of benzoxazinones and benzothiazinones¹⁴², hydrolysis of nitriles¹⁴³, oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols¹⁴⁴ can be done in MW.

Y = O, S

Heck cross coupling reaction¹⁴⁵ can be done in same way under solventless liquid-liquid phase transfer catalytic conditions in presence of potassium carbonate.

Aromatic aldoximes were converted to the corresponding nitriles in microwave oven in the presence of a molecular sieve-type modified zeolite, Ersorb, under solvent free conditions¹⁴⁶.

A novel and efficient synthesis of *N*-arylamines by the reaction of activated aryl halides with secondary amines in the presence of basic Al_2O_3 under microwave irradiation in solvent free conditions is reported¹⁴⁷.

A fast, highly efficient and environmentally friendly, solvent free procedure under microwave irradiation using silica gel supported reagents for the synthesis of melamines is also developed¹⁴⁸. There are some reactions which takes place in MW under solvent free conditions. Like deactivated and sterically hindered phenols have been acetylated with acetic anhydride using iodine as catalyst in an ecofriendly process¹⁴⁹.

(3) Sonochemistry :

Ultrasound is defined as sound of a frequency, which is beyond human hearing i.e. above 16 kHz. It has been reported that chemical reactivity of a system increases on irradiating it with power ultrasound. The study of effects of ultrasound on chemical reactivity is termed as sonochemistry. Some important applications of ultrasound in chemical synthesis are given below :

Ultrasound : 91% yield, no exotherm, no iodine
No Ultrasound : 51% yield, unpredictable exotherm, iodine

Many other examples of sonochemistry assisted organic synthesis like addition reaction, oxidation, reduction, hydroboration, coupling reactions, etc. have been reported^{156,157}. An improved synthesis of chalcones under ultrasound irradiation has been reported by Li *et al.*¹⁵⁸. The yields were 52–97% and 83–98% respectively with pulverized KOH and KF- Al_2O_3 catalysts in alcoholic solvent. An improved preparation of ionic liquids by ultrasound has been reported¹⁵⁹.

Ultrasound assisted organic synthesis gives excellent yields compared to other reactions. Combination of sonication with other techniques, e.g. microwave, phase transfer, photocatalysis, etc. gives best results. Ultrasound technique is also useful in treatment of various pollutants. Sonochemical degradation of toxic halogenated organic compounds¹⁶⁰, volatile pollutants in natural ground water¹⁶¹, 2,4,6-trichlorophenol in presence of TiO_2 catalyst¹⁶², textile dyestuff¹⁶³ have been reported.

(4) Electrochemistry :

Electrochemistry is widely used in industry for example in effluent treatment, corrosion prevention and electroplating as well as in electrochemical synthesis. Electrochemical synthesis is a well established technology for major processes such as aluminium and chlorine production. So now a days interest is increasing for clean synthesis of fine chemical by using electrochemistry. The basis of electrochemical synthesis is the electrochemical cell of which there are many types, both batch and continuous flow, with a multitude of electrode variation. Lead, cadmium, zinc and carbon electrodes are quite often used.

The only large volume application in organic chemistry appears to be the hydromerization of acrylonitrile to form adiponitrile (200000 tons/year) which is then reduced to the hexamethylenediamine or hydrolysed to adipic acid for the preparation of Nylon 6,6¹⁶⁴. Electrochemistry can be used to regenerate an expensive or toxic reagent *in situ*. It is used to generate sodium hypiodite and sodium hydroxide continuously for the epoxidation of 2-methylnaphthoquinone¹⁶⁵. Yield is 100% and no waste is produced.

Electricity can be used in oxidation and reductions instead of reagents. When iodine is reduced to hydroiodic acid in this way¹⁶⁶, no waste products are formed. Naphthalene can be oxidized to naphthoquinone with 98% selectivity using a small amount of cerium salt in aqueous methanesulfonic acid when the cerium(III) that forms is reoxidized to cerium(IV) electrically¹⁶⁷.

Substituted aromatic compounds can be oxidized to the corresponding phenols electrically with a platinum electrode in trifluoroacetic acid, triethylamine and methylene chloride¹⁶⁸. Ketones can be converted to alcohols in upto 98% yield by electrocatalytic hydrogenation using rhodium-modified electrodes¹⁶⁹. An oxidation using a nickel hydroxide electrode is done¹⁷⁰. Hydrogenation of edible oils using a cell with a Nafion membrane with a ruthenium anode on one side and a platinum or palladium black cathode on the other produced less of the undesirable *trans*-isomers than conventional hydrogenations¹⁷¹.

Electrochemistry also provides a way to produce radicals and anions¹⁷².

Synthesis of 3-bromothiophene through 2,3,5-tribromothiophene provides an example of the obvious environmental benefits of an electrochemical route compared to a conventional process because the use of metal reducing agent is avoided and no bromine is wasted. The electrochemical hydrogenation of water immiscible olefins and acetylenes is enhanced by concurred ultrasonication¹⁷³. Tetramethyl adipic acid, a starting monomer for several tech-

nically important polymers is synthesized by direct carbon-carbon bond formation between the saturated primary carbon atom of pivalic acid using a sonoelectrochemical Fenton process¹⁷⁴.

Electrochemistry is used on a large scale in the production of organic and inorganic compound. Reduction of carboxylic acids, nitro compounds and nitriles has been widely reported. Oxidation of aromatics and methyl aromatics has also been studied. Other important inorganic compound like chlorine and sodium hydroxide etc. are manufactured using electrochemical technology. Electrochemical treatment processes can provide valuable contribution to the protection of environment through the minimization of waste and toxic materials in effluents. Electrochemical treatment of distillery effluent using catalytic anodes was reported by Manishankar *et al.*¹⁷⁵.

Traditionally, synthesis of molecules involves use of chemicals, which are hazardous and also put at risk both the human beings and environment. Also, tightening and more universal legislation over the use of hazardous chemicals may indirectly hinder or prevent manufacturing of many important chemical products. Green Chemistry as applied to chemical processes can be environmentally benign (in terms of reduction of energy, auxiliaries, waste, etc.) and should always lead to simplification of processes in terms of chemicals used and steps involved. Thus, if we can develop an efficient chemical synthesis (economically and technologically viable), which incorporates human and environmental good as its core principle, then we truly have sustainable green chemical processing. This can be achieved by applying the principles of **Green Chemistry** to all aspects of science and engineering.

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